

THE USE OF PARALLEL COMPUTING ALGORITHMS IN SOLVING PROBLEMS OF FILTRATION PROCESSES IN OIL FIELDS.

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In this article, we review an algorithm for parallel computing and a software for conducting computational experiments developed on the basis of a mathematical model of filtration processes in oil fields. The developed algorithm of parallel computing and software serve to reduce the time for computational processes and increases the efficiency of designing in oil fields.

Keywords: fluid filtration, parallel computing algorithm, modeling method, porous medium, oil, software.

In recent years, there have been significant shifts in the organization of scientific research due to the widespread implementation of multiprocessor supercomputers. High-performance computing technology in its current form - in the form of massively parallel systems - is a powerful tool that allows you to accelerate progress in solving particularly complex problems of fundamental science and applied research. Over the past decade, scientific research has been conducted in our country in the oil and gas production industry to improve the efficiency of oil field development.

In the research of scientists N.Ravshanov, E.Sh.Nazirova [1], the problem of modeling the process of oil filtration in porous media is considered. A brief review of scientific papers devoted to the development of mathematical support for this

problem is given. A mathematical model of the object of research described by a nonlinear partial differential equation has been developed.

The model is represented by a complete nonlinear equation of hydrodynamics in a three-dimensional formulation. When solving the problem of oil filtration in a porous medium, the main problem arose during the approach of boundary conditions on wells by finite-difference ratios. Therefore, a parallel algorithm was developed to solve it, in which the finite difference method was applied for filtration processes in oil fields.

The transformation of a nonlinear oil filtration algorithm into a computer parallel algorithm with divided tasks into crystals of multiprocessor computing systems with performance allows us to investigate and improve mathematical algorithms for oil filtration problems [2]. The parallel calculation algorithm makes it possible to increase the efficiency of oil development and reduces the time for computational processes in comparison with sequential algorithms on current block calculations by 15-30%, depending on the number and power of processors.

Figure 1. Results comparison of sequential and parallel algorithms on a dual-core Intel Celeron N3060 processor with a frequency of 2.8 GHz

The graph shows that the time to solve the problem in blocks when $N = 30$ points when using a parallel computational algorithm (Fig.1) exceeds by relatively 17.2% than the sequential algorithm.

Number of points XN by YN	Sequential algorithm time(seconds)	Parallel algorithm time(seconds)	Efficiency %
30	3.104	2.568	17.2
100	8.061	10.191	20,2
200	18.507	12.534	32.2
300	24.835	16.341	34.2

Table 1. Results of comparison of sequential and parallel algorithms on a dual-core Intel Celeron N3060 processor with a frequency of 2.8 GHz, when N=30, 100, 100, 300 points, t=720 days

t days	Sequential algorithm time(seconds)	Parallel algorithm time(seconds)	Efficiency %
360	14.582	9.478	35.1
720	24.835	16.341	34.2
1080	32.488	24.991	23.1

Table 2. Results of comparison of sequential and parallel algorithms on a dual-core Intel Celeron N3060 processor with a frequency of 2.8 GHz by days when t=360, 720, 1080 days and XN=300, YN=300

As can be seen from the visualization of the research results (table 2), the use of parallel computing algorithms for calculating oil filtration processes in porous medium between 360 to 1080 days reduces the calculation time by 23-35% on a dual-core processor with a frequency of 2.8 GHz. Thanks to the use of new parallel algorithms on high-performance multiprocessor computing systems with high performance, oil fields modeling efficiency increases and will give significant advances in solving computational problems of oil field development.

Literature

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